

MANAGING WITHIN-CLASS TARGET VARIABILITY IN SAR IMAGERY WITH A TARGET DECOMPOSITION MODEL

Dalton S. Rosario

U.S. Army Research Laboratory
2800 Powder Mill Road
Adelphi, MD 20783-1197
(301) 394-4235
rosario@arl.mil

ABSTRACT

Modifications in a target's signature caused by minor variations in the target can severely limit the robustness of most techniques designed to find targets in synthetic aperture radar (SAR) imagery. This lack of robustness is a pressing issue for SAR. Part of the problem, perhaps, is that targets have been considered as single units and hence features have been extracted with the assumption of radar cross section (RCS) stability everywhere in their footprints. The author demonstrates the advantage of not considering targets as single units; instead, a target is considered in terms of a spatially decomposed model. The model exploits multiple RCS regions in targets. The key features in the model are that (1) targets can be spatially decomposed into useful RCS regions, (2) pixel values in the target are independent random variables in quarter power, (3) the metric σ_i/μ_i determines the level of RCS stability in these regions, and (4) the random variables pertaining to stable regions are Gaussian distributed. The utility of this model is illustrated through a study case involving a serious problem of signature variability.

INTRODUCTION

Contributions to the field of pattern recognition have come from many disciplines, including statistics, communication theory, biology, psychology, and computer science. No single theory of pattern recognition embraces all the important topics, because each domain of application has unique characteristics that mold and shape the appropriate approach.

The most prominent domain-independent theory in this field is classification theory [1]. Based on statistical decision theory, classification theory provides formal mathematical procedures for classifying patterns once they have been represented abstractly as vectors. Attempts to find domain-independent procedures for constructing these vector representations have not yielded generally useful results. Instead, every problem area has acquired a collection of procedures suited to its special characteristics.

The synthetic aperture radar (SAR) community relies on studying the images of various objects of interest, or targets, to determine fundamental differences in their signatures; these differences, or similarities, are used in the development of what might be called *data-driven models*. Data-driven models are based on a set of consistent characteris-

tics found in signatures (given some assumptions) which is reasonably invariant to the target type. (For instance, it has been found that in all manmade objects, most of the power is contained within a few pixels.) A key requirement for the development of such models, however, is the availability of a large database of well-calibrated, truthed, and high-quality SAR imagery of various target types.

Modifications in the signature caused by minor variations in the target, however, can severely limit the robustness of most techniques designed to distinguish targets in SAR imagery. This lack of robustness is one of the most pressing issues in the field of SAR pattern recognition. Part of the problem, perhaps, is that targets have been considered as single units, and therefore, features have been extracted with the assumption that the radar cross section (RCS or σ_{total}) response of targets is stable everywhere in their footprints. I will demonstrate the advantage of not considering a target as a single unit, but instead as a spatially decomposed model. Features derived from this model can be used to design robust pattern recognition algorithms.

The model exploits characteristics of multiple RCS regions in targets. The key features in this model are that (1) the target can be spatially decomposed into useful RCS regions; (2) pixel values in the target are represented by independent random variables, x_i , and mapped into quarter power, or square root of magnitude; (3) the metric σ_i/μ_i (where σ_i = standard deviation and μ_i = mean) measured from the training set is used as a model to determine the level of RCS stability in these regions; and (4) the random variables pertaining to RCS-stable regions are Gaussian distributed, $N(\mu_i, \sigma_i)$.

One can use the properties in these regions to derive discriminating features in targets and to wisely determine areas in the target most suitable for estimating a global compensation factor for the image. (Global adjustment is necessary for many algorithms in order to compensate for radar miscalibration and weather attenuation.) Features derived from this model were used to design a pattern recognition algorithm that yielded excellent results in distinguishing an interesting target deployed in various conditions [2,3].

I focus in this paper on the utility of the target decomposition model for managing within-class target signature variability. I describe the information that forms the model and show its utility for a particular case that illustrates the seriousness of the variability problem.

THE TARGET DECOMPOSITION MODEL

The target decomposition model relies on the fact that targets in SAR imagery can be decomposed into multiple RCS regions. In this study, three RCS regions were identified as useful for feature development. These regions consist of low, medium, and high power levels. The total RCS, σ_{total} for the target is, therefore,

$$\sigma_{total} = \sigma_{low} + \sigma_{medium} + \sigma_{high}.$$

An important aspect about this decomposition is that these regions have properties that are invariant to the target type: whether it is a truck or a tank, these properties are observed. But since the spatial relationship among these regions depends on the target type, the features developed based on region characteristics are discriminatory from one object to another.

PROPERTIES OF RCS REGIONS

Low-power RCS region: When the signature of a target is properly decomposed, the low-power region is characterized by an area consisting of a small percentage (about 15 percent) of the target's total RCS. The energy in this region, as seen by the SAR, is primarily the result of backscattered energy delayed by multi-bounce effects and of echoes from weak scatterers in the target. The contribution of multi-bounce energy in this region is highly dependent on the target's aspect angle with respect to the sensor. This effect is most prominent when the target is posed near/at 90° or 270° and least prominent when it is posed near/at 0° or 180° . Despite the dependence between the RCS fluctuation and the target orientation, this dark region corresponds to the same portion of the footprint when multiple instances of the target, at some orientation, are observed. It can be shown that the RCS fluctuation in this region is stable, having small values of σ_i/μ_i . Since this region has a stable RCS, the distribution of x_i is assumed to be Gaussian in the quarter-power domain.

Medium-power RCS region: The medium-power region is characterized by brighter scatterers representing most of the target. For all targets observed in the lab, this region has the most stable RCS compared to the other two: it has small and uniform values of σ_i/μ_i . When the target is properly decomposed, the spatial pattern of this region is also a reliable feature. Since this region has a stable RCS, the distribution of x_i is also assumed to be Gaussian.

High-power RCS region: The high-power region is characterized by a few *specularities* in the target (typically 5 to 10 percent of the brightest pixels) consisting of most of the target's reflected energy. The target's RCS is highly unstable in this region, having large values of σ_i/μ_i . A reasonable procedure to estimate the spatial pattern for this region is to find the spatial distribution of the brightest scatterers in multiple instances of the target, at some nominal azimuth, and to perform a logical OR operation with these spatial distributions. The resultant spatial pattern in the target's footprint can be used as a reliable feature for this region.

These three regions partition the target footprint. This partition allows us to form multi-RCS-region masks to fully

represent the target in various orientations. These masks can be used to focus on different target regions before feature extraction.

A SIMPLE EXAMPLE WITH A BIG IMPACT

To illustrate the utility of the target decomposition model, let's consider the case of the Heavy Expanded Mobility Tactical Truck (HEMTT). Figure 1 depicts the optical and the SAR images of two HEMTTs, serial numbers 501 and 512. An obvious difference between the two SAR images is the absence of a dominant echo from an expected corner reflector in HEMTT 512. During the aperture time, HEMTT 512 had the radar-facing corner in its cargo bay slightly open, which caused most of the expected backscatter energy to disperse. The impact of this minor variation in the target can be catastrophic for most metrics for pattern recognition, especially when either one of these extreme cases is used as a reference to find a larger class of the HEMTT. For instance, if HEMTT 501 is used as the reference in this case, the energy reflected from the dominant corner reflector will drive the estimation of crucial algorithm parameters, which in turn will determine on-line operational ranges, drive on-line estimation of the image global-compensation factor, and interfere with the effectiveness of the features. One reasonable way to minimize the problems in this case is to use images of both vehicles to represent the target; however, one rarely finds enough instances of the target variance, and obviously, this is far from a generalized solution.

For this experiment, one image per degree in azimuth was collected for a full coverage of 360° , in five elevation angles, yielding a total of 1800 images for each truck. The HEMTT 501 images were used as references; at every 5° of azimuth, 15 neighboring images (five instances in azimuth times three elevation angles) were averaged out to robustly represent this target at 72 azimuthal regions. The decomposition of one of these averaged images is shown in Figure 2, along with its corresponding decomposition template. A three-dimensional representation for this decomposition is shown in Figure 3, along with the corresponding information from the decomposition model.

Figure 1. High-resolution (1x1 ft) SAR images of two military trucks collected by a sensor working at Ku band with a single VV polarization. Illumination path is from bottom to top of images.

FEATURES FROM DECOMPOSITION MODEL

The information from the decomposition model can be used to derive features. Figure 4 depicts three discriminant features and the RCS region in the target most suitable to have the global compensation factor estimated for the image. The rationale for the features shown in Figure 4 is as follows:

(1) The mean square error (MSE) works at pixel i if the distribution of x_i in both test and training examples is the same. The RCS fluctuation in both low- and medium-power RCS regions is stable and the distribution of their pixels is assumed Gaussian; thus the mean of pointwise square errors is a suitable discriminating feature for these two regions.

(2) It can be shown that the best region in the image for estimating a global compensation factor is the one with a large number of the pixels and having small values of σ_i/μ_i . Since the low- and medium-power RCS target regions represent most of the target and have stable RCS fluctuation, these combined regions should be used for estimating the global compensation factor.

(3) The RCS fluctuation in the high-power RCS region is unstable, but the spatial distribution of its scatterers is reliable. Order statistics can be used, in this region, to find the spatial distribution of these scatterers. The template's brightest region (Figure 2) shows where the spatial distribution of the brightest scatterers should intersect for the HEMTT at 45° in azimuth and 42° in elevation.

(4) The power gap between the mutually exclusive low- and high-power RCS regions is also a strong feature, since its expected value depends on the spatial relationship between these two regions, and fortunately, this spatial relationship is a characteristic of the target type. A metric least affected by unstable RCS, however, such as the *median* value, should be used to represent the high-power RCS region.

FEATURE EFFECTIVENESS RESULTS

These features were measured for the HEMTT 501 and tested against the HEMTT 512 (see Figures 5 and 6). The MSE feature was developed based on the central-limit theorem (sample version); since it computes the square of a linear function that depends on a Gaussian random variable, the MSE has N chi-squared distributed functions (when N = number of pixels), with a normalized cumulative expected value equal to unity. This indicates that if the candidate target is in fact the HEMTT 501, its MSE performance is expected to be around the value of 1.0 in Figure 5.

The MSE between the 501 and 512 HEMTTs is shown, in Figure 5, for each of the 1800 HEMTT 512 images ranging from 0° to 360° in azimuth. The small triangles represent the MSE calculated using the HEMTT's footprint as the mask (this procedure is usual in the pattern-recognition field), and the small squares represent the MSE calculated using both the low- and medium-power RCS regions as the mask (this is the procedure I propose for robustness in performance). Notice the performance of the latter, which scores around 1.0, contrasted to the former, which shows a dra-

Figure 2. HEMTT 501 decomposed into three radar-cross section regions: low, medium, and high power. Decomposition yields a robust template (right), depicting expected spatial relationship between regions for this target.

Figure 3. Three-dimensional representation of decomposed HEMTT 501: properties of three RCS regions.

Figure 4. Examples of features based on target decomposition model.

matic difference between the two vehicles (particularly between 0° and 90° , where the open corner in HEMTT 512 is exposed to the radar).

In Figure 6, the global compensation factor estimated to adjust the images to a baseline level is shown. Since these images were already calibrated, the expected value for this estimate is 0 dB. Each value in Figure 6 represents the average compensation factor estimated for each group of 15 images across azimuth. The crosses show this factor estimated for the HEMTT 501, which is at the baseline level, using its footprint as the mask; the triangles show this factor estimated for the HEMTT 512 also using the footprint as the mask; and the squares show this factor estimated for the HEMTT 512 this time using the most reliable RCS regions in the target: the low- and medium-power RCS regions, as suggested in the model. The global compensation estimates for the HEMTT 501 are stable in azimuth and closer to 0 dB, as is expected. The compensation factors estimated for the HEMTT 512 using the footprint, however, are farther away from 0 dB and very unstable, most noticeably around azimuth angles where the open corner was facing the sensor. The compensation factors estimated for the HEMTT 512, using the low- and medium-power RCS regions as the mask, are closer to 0 dB and more stable, which also supports the claim of robustness against this difficult case of signature variability.

Similar performances can be shown for other targets and for other features derived from the target decomposition model. For instance, one can exploit the reliable spatial distribution of targets' brightest scatterers by adaptively searching and checking for the locations of a few of them.

FINAL REMARKS

The utility of spatially decomposing target signatures to assist in deriving robust features has been demonstrated. The effectiveness of using the target's whole signature was contrasted with that of using characteristics of multiple RCS regions in the target. The key feature in the model is that most targets in SAR images can be "artificially" decomposed into three useful RCS regions. The target decomposition model was formed from common characteristics of these three regions observed in targets. A set of simple but robust features was derived with this model and demonstrated to be robust against a difficult problem of target-signature variability. A pattern-recognition algorithm based on these features was successfully demonstrated in a real-time field test [3].

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Figure 5. MSE results between HEMTT 501 and HEMTT 512 as a function of azimuth angle. Small triangles: individual scores for HEMTT 512 using whole signature; small squares: scores using decomposed low- and medium-power RCS regions combined.

Figure 6. Global compensation factor estimated between HEMTT 501 and 512 to adjust for expected radar miscalibration and weather attenuation (factor is expected to be around 0 dB). Crosses: average estimated factor for HEMTT 501 using the full signature; triangles: estimates for HEMTT 512 using full signature; squares: results for HEMTT 512 using low- and medium-power RCS regions.